

Multi-Fidelity Neural Network Approach for Warpage Prediction and Optimization in Injection Molding

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Motivation for Studying Warpage

Warpage in injection molding

Causes of warpage

Integrated Simulation and Experimental Framework for Injection Molding Analysis

Simulation data

Experimental data

Melt Temp. (°C)	Inj. Speed (cm ³ /s)	Pack Press. (MPa)	Pack Time (s)
225	20	20	1
230	30	30	2
235	40	40	3
240	50	50	4
245	60	60	5

Multi-Fidelity Neural Network framework

X. Meng, G.E. Karniadakis (2019)

$$y_H = \rho(x)y_L + \delta(x)$$

$$y_H = F(y_L) + \delta(x)$$

$$y_H = \mathcal{F}(x, y_L)$$

Multi-Fidelity Neural Network framework

Multi-fidelity Gaussian Process Regression (Multi-fidelity GPR)

$$k(x, x') = \underbrace{C \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{\|x - x'\|^2}{2l^2}\right)}_{\text{RBF Kernel}} + \underbrace{\sigma_n^2 \delta(x - x')}_{\text{White noise}}$$

A scaling parameter

$$\rho_j = \frac{\langle Y_L^{(j)}, Y_H^{(j)} \rangle}{\|Y_L^{(j)}\|^2}$$

Difference between fidelities

- C is a constant kernel
- l is the RBF length scale.
- σ_n^2 is the noise variance
- $\delta(x - x')$ is the Kronecker delta function

$$f_H(x) = \rho \cdot f_L(x) + \delta(x)$$

Prediction from the **low-fidelity**

Predicting Experimental Data (High-Fidelity data)

25 samples for High-Fidelity data

Performance of Gaussian Process Regression on Low-Fidelity data

$$X = \{x^{(1)}, x^{(2)}, \dots, x^{(n)}\}$$

$$\tilde{x}^{(i)} = x^{(i)} + \varepsilon^{(i)}, \quad \varepsilon^{(i)} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_x^2 I)$$

- $\tilde{x}^{(i)}$: Noisy input
- $\varepsilon^{(i)}$: Gaussian noise
- σ_x : Noise standard deviation

Function Sampling from Gaussian Process Regression

$$X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$$

$$f(x) \sim \mathcal{GP}(\mu(x), k(x, x'))$$

Mean Vector

$$\mu = \begin{bmatrix} \mu(x_1) \\ \vdots \\ \mu(x_n) \end{bmatrix}$$

Covariance Matrix:

$$\Sigma = \begin{bmatrix} k(x_1, x_1) & \cdots & k(x_1, x_n) \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ k(x_n, x_1) & \cdots & k(x_n, x_n) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\text{samples} = \mu + L \cdot \varepsilon, \quad \varepsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I)$$

$$L = \text{Cholesky}(\Sigma)$$

$$f^{(s)}(x_1), \dots, f^{(s)}(x_n)$$

Performance of Multi-Fidelity Gaussian Process Regression

$+\delta(x)$
 $), \Sigma_L(x))$
 $\Sigma_\delta(x))$
 $) + \delta^{(s)}(x)$

Performance of Neural Network on Simulation data

$$\text{Input noise: } \tilde{x} = x + \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_x^2 I)$$

$$\text{Output noise: } \tilde{y} = y + \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_y^2 I)$$

Performance of Multi-Fidelity Neural Network

$$\hat{y}_L = \mathcal{N}_L(x_L)$$

$$\hat{y}_H = \mathcal{F}(x_H) = \mathcal{N}_H(x_H, \mathcal{N}_L(x_H))$$

Artificially Intelligent Manufacturing Paradigm for Composites

Cross Disciplinary Work: Thrusts III + II

Partner Institutions

